

SOUTHERN AFRICAN HYDROGEN AND FUEL CELL CONFERENCE 2023

24-25 APRIL 2023

HAZENDAL WINE ESTATE, STELLENBOSCH, CAPE TOWN

From fundamentals to accelerated integration

ECOSA AND SACNASP CPD POINTS WILL BE ALLOCATED PER HOUR ATTENDED

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

The primary purpose of the 1st Hydrogen and Fuel Cells conference is the advancement of green hydrogen technologies in Southern Africa and the global community, by highlighting the power of renewable and sustainable technologies and addressing the emerging challenges—through the exploration of fuel cells, hydrogen storage, and hydrogen generation by way of engagement with industry, academia and government. The conference will provide a platform for high level exchange and networking opportunities with various experts in the field. The two-day conference will feature high-level scientific talks and posters, complemented with keynote and plenary presentations on country overviews, status of leading and major players in the Southern African and global arena.

BENEFITS OF ATTENDING

- ◆ Will include both inspiring technical talks as well as social networking events
- ◆ Participants will have the opportunity to directly engage with conference participants to discuss their research

- ◆ Engagement opportunities with fellow researchers, potential collaborators, industry, and potential investors.

TOPICS

- ◆ Fuel cell technologies & applications
- ◆ Performance, durability, design, and manufacturing (from components to systems)
 - Hydrogen storage technologies
 - Hydrogen generation technologies
- ◆ Hydrogen mobility – strategies, safety, roadmaps, transitioning to hydrogen refueling stations (HRS)
- ◆ Technology status in industry.

WHO SHOULD ATTEND

The conference presents an attractive programme for researchers, industry players, academic institutions, government, investors, policy makers and potential users of fuel cell and hydrogen technologies. The focus is on building collective know-how and fostering engagement between business, government, science and academic institutions. Participants from all countries are invited and welcome to attend the event.

CALL FOR ABSTRACTS

Extended abstracts, presentations only or full papers can be submitted for this conference, please take note of the following deadline dates.

- Abstract Submission Deadline for Extended Abstracts and Presentations Only: 28 February 2023
- Submission Deadline for Extended Abstracts: 20 March 2023
- Abstract Submission Deadline for Full Papers: 9 January 2023
- Submission Deadline for Papers: 13 February 2023.

The Conference is being organized by the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy, and individuals are invited to submit papers or presentations or posters for the Conference. Titles and short abstracts (no more than 500 words) on any relevant subject should be submitted in English to:

Head of Conferencing,
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SAIMM
THE SOUTHERN AFRICAN INSTITUTE
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PEM Fuel Cell Powered Forklift Utilising Advanced Metal Hydride Hydrogen Storage and Refuelling at Impala Platinum Refineries

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In 2016, a hydrogen-powered electric forklift together with an accompanying hydrogen refuelling station was commissioned at Impala Platinum Refineries, Springs, South Africa. The deployment is part of an Impala Platinum-funded collaboration project between HySA Systems Centre of Competence, hosted by the University of the Western Cape, and South African engineering company, TF Design (Pty) Ltd.

The project entailed the development of a hydrogen storage and supply system for an electric forklift (3 ton lifting capacity, 80 VDC bus voltage) equipped with a commercial low temperature Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) power module. The system, shown in Figure 1, combines hydrogen storage in a composite gas cylinder (CGH₂), which forms part of the power module, and a metal hydride (MH) extension tank thermally integrated with the power module. The MH tank uses an AB₂-type hydrogen storage alloy characterised by hydrogen equilibrium pressures above 10 bar at temperatures higher than 20 °C. The alloy is disposed in MH containers built according to an original HySA Systems design that enables improved heat exchange performance. This allows easy activation of the MH material and fast H₂ charge / discharge rates. The combined CGH₂+MH hydrogen storage system, at a pressure of no more than 185 bar, has the same hydrogen storage capacity (~19 Nm³ H₂) as the separate CGH₂ tank charged at a pressure of 350 bar. This lower storage pressure allows for a significant reduction in indirect costs associated with hydrogen refuelling without any penalty in refuelling time (ca. 15 minutes).

The refuelling station utilizes H₂ that is provided by pipeline at 50-60 bar, as well as other services including steam, cooling water, compressed air and electricity available at Impala Platinum Refineries. The H₂ dispensing pressure is stepped up by means of an integrated thermally driven MH H₂ compressor to a pressure of 185 bar.

The implementation of this new concept of integrating MHs in a forklift as on-board hydrogen storage and as a thermally driven MH compressor in the refuelling system is shown in Figure 2. Since its commissioning, the forklift has been in operation without any major operational issues. Service of the equipment is provided periodically (at least once a year) by HySA Systems and TF Design.

The implementation of novel locally developed hydrogen technology will offer Impala Platinum a decisive opportunity to successfully implement a Hydrogen Economy process in the core of its Refining operations.

Figure 1. General system concept. A – donor vehicle (forklift). B – on-board fuel cell power module. C: Hydrogen storage tank. D: Stationary hydrogen refuelling system with integrated metal hydride hydrogen compressor.

Figure 2. Refuelling of the fuel cell forklift at Impala Platinum Refineries using hydrogen refuelling station with integrated MH hydrogen compressor shown in call-out picture (right)